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Engineering, Technology and Applied Sciences

Comparative Analysis of Coir Fiber, Banana Fiber, and Synthetic Fibers for Sustainable Composites

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Abstract

This research presents the mechanical properties of reinforced bio-composites using coir and banana fibers with the aim aiming to identify viable ecological replacements to conventional glass fiber reinforced composites. The samples were prepared with natural fiber such as coir and banana. Samples were tested for hardness (ASTM E10), impact energy (ASTM D256), and wear resistance (ASTM G99) tests, while making comparative benchmarks with E- glass and S-glass polyester composites. The Brinell hardness numbers indicated that banana fiber composites were harder than coir fiber composites, outperforming both E-glass and S-glass composites. Both coir and banana fiber composites' impact energy followed with 1.47 J, but lower than the synthetic composites. The wear resistance tests revealed that most coir fiber composites have the least wear percentage, which was at 0.22% , but still higher than the wear percentage in E-glass and S-glass composites. According to these findings, it will suggest that natural fiber-reinforced composites, particularly banana fiber-reinforced composites, possess a higher hardness than conventional glass fiber composites. But they have lower impact energy absorption and higher rates of wear. In other forms of optimization, like fiber treatment or hybridization, could improve such properties and render natural fiber composites. So, they will be more viable alternatives in engineering applications. Further investigations that have been conducted on banana and coconut fiber reinforcement in epoxy composites have revealed that fiber content shows a great influence on mechanical properties. With the optimal fiber weight percentage providing enhanced tensile and impact strengths. Thus, our findings further confirm the feasibility of natural fiber-reinforced composites in the development of green materials with appropriate mechanical properties.

Keywords: *Banana fibre, Coir fibres, Composites, Mechanical properties, Sustainable materials*

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Development of an Automated Bag Feeding System for Small-scale Mushroom Farming

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Abstract

The design of the automated grow bag feeder aims to enhance the efficiency and precision of the filling process by designing and manufacturing a specialized feeding mechanism tailored to the specific requirements of small-scale mushroom cultivation. With mushroom farming automation, directly response to labour shortage and inefficiencies in labour. So, this system proposes a sophisticated solution to facilitate and enhance the entire fill process. This machine includes an advance collection of elements, including a motorised grow bag mouth opening system, with precision-driven gripper and motion systems, an automatic bag holder, and a comprehensive PLC control panel. Some of the most important new features of the design are a vacuum-actuated system that opens and closes grow bags and a lead screw and timing belt setup that makes the whole process smooth and controlled. The repositioning of NEMA (National Electrical Manufacturers Association) motors, aluminium V profiles, and a powerful conveyor system ensures continued handling of grow bags with minimum intervention while ensuring optimal alignment and speed. A screw conveyor and grow media mixer are also integrated into the design to facilitate efficient filling without disrupting workflow. This automated system does away with such manual interventions, thus ensuring consistent and accurate bag feeding. The PLC control allows for real-time monitoring and operations of the system. This gives the user-friendly interface to monitor and manipulate the processes as needed. The design uses a combination of state-of-the-art motors, stepper drivers, and limit switches to maximise both speed and reliability, dramatically cutting down on operational costs. Automating more critical stages of mushroom production, this up and laudable innovation is set to increase productivity while ensuring cheaper labour and sustainability in agricultural practices. With greatly streamlined processes and enhanced control features, this machine marks a substantial step in the modernisation of mushroom farming operations to gain further growth and profitability in the industry.

Keywords: *Bag feeding unit, Bag holder, Filling machine, Mushroom*

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